

Identification of dried bacteria related to dairy industry using NIR spectral imaging at different spatial scales

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In food safety, the standard method for evaluation of surface contamination involves swabbing the working surfaces and analysing the swab (Lelieveld et al., 2014). The results of this methodology depend on the sampling scheme employed. The application of NIR hyperspectral imaging (NIR-HSI) combined with chemometrics can recognise different types of food-related bacteria, introducing a spatial information absent using traditional approaches. Colonies of bacteria on agar (Kammies et al., 2016) and bacteria on aluminium (Dubois et al., 2005) have been identified using NIR-HSI.

In this study, Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria of relevance to the dairy industry are analysed with a preliminary experiment carried out using *E. coli* and *B. subtilis*. Bacteria were grown in liquid culture and culture media removed by washing with sterile buffer and/or water; 10 µL drops of cell suspension at different concentrations (1–10 optical density [O.D.] measured at 600 nm) were dried on stainless steel slides. The dried bacteria were imaged using Cytoviva Vis-SWIR Nanoscale Hyperspectral Microscope (ImSpector NIR, InGaAs Xeva Camera). The NIR wavelength range of this microscope is 870–1700 nm. Each sample was scanned by using both 10x (numerical aperture [N.A.] 0.25) and 50x (N.A. 0.65) lens, in order to increase the spatial information. Initial principal component analysis (PCA) showed the substantial effect of surface morphology on the spectral imaging data. Different chemometrics approaches were subsequently applied and compared in order to evaluate their performance on bacteria classification.

Keywords: food safety, bacteria, hyperspectral, spectral, imaging, NIR

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